

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE
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Department of Food Processing and Technology

Training Manual

Agro-Processing, Productivity Enhancement and Livelihood
Improvement Support Project Women and Youth Empowerment
Programme.

September 2019

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INTRODUCTION

This training manual is developed for training of women and youths under the Federal Government of Nigeria Productivity Enhancement and Livelihood Improvement Support Project Women and Youths Empowerment Programme. The manual is developed by the Centre for Dryland Agriculture in collaboration with the Departments of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Agronomy, Animal Science, Fisheries and Aquaculture and Food Science and Technology in the Faculty of Agriculture in Bayero University. Kano.

This manual is expected to be used in building the capacity of women and youths who will be trained in the Rice, Poultry and Aquaculture value chain. This training manual is need based and is based on the many years of experiences of staff in the different activities of the rice, poultry and aquaculture value chains. The manual is a tool for the trainers describing the proposed training methodology, objectives, related activities and exercises. It can be adopted to different target audience.

The manual is organised in two parts; A general manual and curriculum for all the trainers and the handout for each value chain. All the trainees are expected to participate in Agribusiness Management; the first component of the manual which will be taken in plenary two to three hours daily. The trainees are expected to acquire Agribusiness Management skills like Value creation, marketing, funds and financial management, leadership and business plan development. The subsequent components of the manual address the fish, poultry and rice value chains with classroom lectures but more emphasis on practical sessions at the poultry farm, fishponds and rice mill.

We will like to acknowledge the contributions of the staff of the contributing Departments for drawing up the training manual.

Prof Amina Mustapha
Deputy Director (Outreach and Publications)

MODULE I: ROLE OF WOMEN AND YOUTHS IN AGRIBUSINESS

1.1 OBJECTIVES

1. Orient women and youths in their roles in food security and development through participation in agricultural and agribusiness activities;
2. Develop appreciation on the importance of policies framework in enhancing greater participation of women and youths in agricultural and agribusiness activities

1.1.1 Activities

- Lectures
- Discussion
- Videos
- Presentation
- Case studies

1.1.2 Time Required: 2 hours (1 hour of teaching and 1 hours of practical session)

1.1.3 Learning Exercises (Brainstorming, group discussion,

- Identify what problems they encounter in the process
- identify what solutions can be forwarded
- share and own the problems and solutions
- find ways to collaborate in order to sustain their empowerment.

1.1.4 Energizers

1.1.5 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop

1.1.6 Evaluation

MODULE II: CAPTURING VALUE IN THE FOOD VALUE CHAIN

2.1 OBJECTIVES

1. To identify the sequence of activities in the food supply chain of the region
2. To understand the relationships of key players in the food supply chain
3. To locate one's farm business and/or agribusiness in the existing food supply chain/ agricultural value chain

2.1.1 Time:

Five (3) hours (1 hour of lecture, 2 hours of practicals)

2.1.2 Activities

- Lectures
- Discussion
- Videos
- Presentation
- Case studies

2.1.3 Time Required: 3 hours (1 hour of teaching and 2 hours of practical session)

2.1.4 Learning Exercises (Brainstorming, group discussion,

2.1.5 Energizers

2.1.6 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop

2.1.7 Evaluation

2.2 THE FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN/VALUE CHAIN AND MARKET OPPORTUNITIES

Figure 1: The Food Value Chain

- Food production is at the core of the food supply chain or value chain. Central to this is the farmer. The farmer is the single most important player in the supply chain. He or she sets the type, pace and inter-relationships in the chain. Without the farmer, there is nothing to integrate downstream or upstream of the supply chain. Thus, to capture the value of the product in the food supply chain is to capture the value of the product at the farmer's level.
- A value chain links the steps a product takes from the farmer to the consumer. It includes research and development, input suppliers and finance. The farmer combines these resources with land, labor and capital to produce commodities (UNIDO, 2009). A segment is a vertical part of a value chain that relates to a certain function, e.g., primary production, first-level processing, second-level processing, or marketing (Henriksen, and Ponte, 2010).
- Land can be owned, rented or tenanted. Labor can be permanent or hired, particularly during planting and harvesting
- Equipment includes farm machineries such as tractors; farm tools; and farm animals. Irrigation can either be privately owned or communal. It can be sourced through pumps, gravity (water flow from springs) or reservoirs. Other materials include fertilizer, pesticides and the like.
- Financing can be obtained through loan or own equity
- Research and Development (R&D) is done to look for optimal resource use and allocation. This can be provided by the governments, universities and research institutions; international organisations and private sector. However, government should be in the forefront of promoting R&D.

2.2.1 Value Chain Marketing System

- In a Value Chain Marketing System (Figure 5), farmers are linked to the needs of consumers, working closely with suppliers and processors to produce the specific goods required by consumers.
- Using this approach, and through continuous innovation and feedback between different stages along the value chain, the farmer's market power and profitability can be enhanced. Rather than focusing profits on one or two links, players at all levels of the value chain can benefit.
- Well-functioning value chains are said to be more efficient in bringing products to consumers and therefore all actors, including small-scale producers and poor consumers, should benefit from value chain development (RIU, 2009).
- The feedback flow also provides farmer the option to establish partnerships with players in the upstream of the food chain or to expand its farm business by engaging in agribusiness activities such as sorting, packing, labelling and/or processing.
- The choice is dependent on the extent of information and skill the farmer has and the financing provided to him/her.
- Farm business must not end at the production level, where after harvest and delivery of products to the market, the farmer ends its link with the food supply chain. There

are a number of activities (as mentioned in the above) which can be done by the farmer (s) to add value to produce.

- Value adding activities from production to the end consumer provides opportunities for more enterprises established, employment generated and higher income through higher price of the product.

E. Exercises

Exercise 1: (this can be done in plenary or in groups)

Objectives

- To obtain a clear understanding of the sequence of activities in the food supply chain/commodity value chain.

Duration: 30 minutes of exercise; 30 minutes of processing

Steps

- What to do:
 - Prepare the value chain of your product from the supply of input to the retail of the commodity to the end consumers?
- How to do it:
 - Name the product you are producing or plan to process
 - Identify the main activities carried out in the value chain from the supply of input to the retail of the commodity to the end consumers.
 - Identify the operators/actors involved in these activities and what are their roles.
 - Draw the flow of activities in a “flow chart”
 - Identify where the commodity originates from and where does it go, using the locality map provided.

Exercise 2: (this can be done in plenary or in groups)

Objectives

- To obtain a clear understanding of the key actors and relationships involved in the food supply chain/commodity value chain.

Duration: 30 minutes of exercise; 30 minutes of processing

Steps

- How does value of the commodity change through the value chain? To answer this in an organized manner, fill-up the information asked in the table below:*

Table 1: Value chain activities

ACTIVITIES IN THE VALUE CHAIN	ACTORS/OPERATORS AND THE ITEMS	PRICE (PHP)/KG	REMARKS IF ANY

b. What types of relationships and linkages exist among the various chain actors? These may include a market relationship, a persistent network relationship between independent firms, a vertical integration, etc. To answer this in an organized manner, fill-up the information asked in the table below:

Table 2: Relationship and linkages between value chain actors

ACTIVITIES IN THE VALUE CHAIN	ACTORS/OPERATORS	RELATIONSHIPS/ LINKAGES

Table 3: Example of value chain activities along the rice value chain in Nigeria

ACTIVITIES IN THE VALUE CHAIN	ACTORS/OPERATORS	RELATIONSHIPS/ LINKAGES
Input Supply	Input suppliers	Support actors especially farmers through the Supply of seed, fertilizer and agrochemicals to farmers
Rice production	Farmer	Produce paddy
Rice processing	Parboiler Miller	Parboil paddy for producers, millers and milled rice traders Mill rice for producers, parboilers and milled rice traders
Rice trading	Paddy trader Milled rice trader	Seller of paddy, make paddy available for parboilers, millers and milled rice traders throughout the year Trades milled rice, making it available throughout the year.

MODULE III: NEW TECHNOLOGY/VALUE CREATION

3.1 OBJECTIVES

- a. To identify and understand value adding processes that are integral to value chain development, in addition to primary agricultural production and marketing;
- b. To be able to document good practices that remained undocumented that can be case worthy for technology and new creation in agribusiness.

3.1.1 Time: 2 hours (30 minutes of lecture and 1 ½ hour of practical session)

3.1.2 Activities

- Lectures
- Discussion
- Videos
- Presentation
- Case studies

3.1.3 Learning Exercises (Brainstorming, group discussion,

3.1.4 Energizers

3.1.5 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop

3.1.6 Evaluation

3.2 AGRIBUSINESS AND VALUE CREATION

3.2.1 What is Agribusiness? (FAO, 2007)

Agribusiness is a broad concept that covers input suppliers, agro-processors, traders, exporters and retailers. Agribusiness provides inputs to farmers and connects them to consumers through the financing, handling, processing, storage, transportation, marketing and distribution of agro-industry products and can be decomposed further into four main groups:

1. Agricultural input industry for increasing agricultural productivity, such as agricultural machinery, equipment and tools; fertilizers, pesticides, insecticides; irrigation systems and related equipment;

2. Agro-industry: Food and beverages; tobacco products, leather and leather products; textile, footwear and garment; wood and wood products; rubber products; as well as construction industry products based on agricultural materials;
3. Equipment for processing agricultural raw materials, including machinery, tools, storage facilities, cooling technology and spare parts;
4. Various services, financing, marketing and distribution firms, including storage, transport, ICTs, packaging materials and design for better marketing and distribution. Agribusiness is thus a term used to mean farming plus all the other industries and services that constitute the supply chain from farm through processing, wholesaling and retailing to the consumer (from farm to fork in the case of food products).

3.2.2 Agribusiness and technology (Baptista, 2012)

The use of technology in agribusinesses is not a recent development. People have used various forms of technology in production for centuries. In every period, new patterns of behavior were required as technology developed and changed the way work was done. In general, though, compared with other industries agribusiness technology has been rustic.

3.2.3 Strategies for New Creation (Riisgaard & Ponte 2011)

Figure 7: Framework of Value Chain Strategies

Source: Riisgaard et al. (2008):

1. Improve Process, Product or Volume

This type of strategy is about ‘doing things better or bigger’ through improvements in technology and management. They include:

- Process improvement: Efficiency in production processes can be increased and costs or negative externalities can be reduced. This includes delivering on schedule, proper invoicing, improving client management, reducing wastage, etc.
- Product improvement: Here the aim is to move into more ‘sophisticated’ products, increasing unit value by complying with buyer requirements for physical quality, certification, food safety standards, traceability, packaging etc.
- Volume extension: The object is to increase the amount of product sold through increases in yield or area in agricultural production, extension of processing capacities and expansion of markets. Increasing volume must not be a goal per se, but is useful if value addition is also generated and distributed to a higher number of actors across the chain (larger volumes can also be achieved by aggregating orders, e.g. by creating a common export desk serving farmer groups). Shifting production to bulk-commodity markets to gain from economies of scale and reduce risks can also be a strategy.

2. Change and/or Add Functions

Value chain actors can take on board new functions, for example by performing downstream activities such as grading, processing, bulking, transporting or advertising or by engaging in the provision of services, inputs or finance. Value chain actors can also engage in functional ‘downgrading’, e.g. dropping processing activities to specialize in production. For producer organizations, engaging in processing and marketing may increase their margins but often they are not sufficiently prepared for this. New functions should only be entered into when these organizations can perform existing functions efficiently and bear the additional risks.

3. Improve Value Chain Coordination

Small agricultural producers in developing countries are typically linked to agro-processors and buyers through market transactions. These transactions can adopt characteristics that tend to reduce rewards and/or increase risks for producers, often with negative ramifications along the entire chain. Value chain development can work towards improved forms of co-ordination. *Vertical and horizontal contracting are examples of such opportunities:*

- Vertical contracting between actors from different segments in the chain, e.g. between farmers and wholesalers or processors and retailer, etc. This means ‘getting a better deal’ through closer and longer-term business ties. It represents a move away from informal transactions to the use of contracts (oral or written). Sellers can ‘learn from buyers’ (about market requirements and compliance with quality specifications) and buyers can embed services in the contract with regard to the extension, credit, and equipment they provide (interlocking contracts). The benefits of such contracts

include the reduction of price risks, access to price premiums, improved access to market information, inputs and finance or reduced marketing costs. But contracts also demand higher performance in relation to quality, volume, and certification, which is often difficult and costly for poor farmers and resource-poor processors

- Horizontal contracting between actors from the same segment, between farmers, SMEs, co-ops, etc. These are agreements among value chain actors to co-operate regarding input provision, marketing (for example, bulking produce for sale, identification of buyers), certification, and crop insurance in order to reduce costs, increase revenues or mitigate risks. For producers, this is often a precondition to reach volume sizes requested by buyers; it can strengthen producers' bargaining power.

Contracting can enhance overall vertical and horizontal chain performance in situations where continuous supply of primary and processed materials in sufficient quality and quantity is of concern to buyers. However, value chain actors may also resist vertical and horizontal contracting because it threatens their position in the chain; for example, middlemen may want to prevent farmers from selling in bulk directly to wholesalers. (Riisgaard & Ponte 2011)

D1. Exercise (Plenary or in group)

- a. Students to document good practices in agribusiness
- b. Evaluate these good practices in terms of its technological cost and efficiency

Duration: 30 minutes of exercise; 1 hour of processing

MODULE IV: SOURCES OF FUNDS, FUND MANAGEMENT AND RECORD KEEPING

4.1 OBJECTIVES

1. Explain the various sources and principles of funding for agribusiness, entrepreneurship or farm ownership.
2. Identify possible sources of funds for the business.
3. Internalize the basic elements of fund management
4. Explain record keeping and types in agribusiness
5. Identify risks in business and types of risks

4.1.1 Time: 3 hours

4.1.2 Activities

- Lectures
- Discussion
- Videos
- Presentation
- Case studies

4.1.3 Learning Exercises (Brainstorming, group discussion,

4.1.4 Energizers

4.1.5 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop

4.1.6 Evaluation

4.2 Sources of Funds and Fund Management

4.2.1 Farm Credit/Financing in Agribusiness.

4.2.1.1 Sources of funds

- Many farmers and small business owners source their start-up capital from their own pocket. They also borrow from relatives and friends.
- Others borrow from small lending associations and cooperatives
- Another common source, particularly from among micro entrepreneurs is loan sharks or usurers.
- Debt financing is borrowing money from another source (creditor, for instance, banks), which the borrower has to pay back according to the agreed

upon payment terms. For bank loans, entrepreneurs with a proven capacity to repay debt are favoured.

- Government is intensifying its assistance programs to small enterprises and farmers, introducing new ones, and bring them down to the grassroots level. One of this is in microfinance where micro and small enterprises can borrow small but quick money from government-accredited institutions at easy repayment terms. There are other microfinance outlets that are privately owned and can be a source of funds even though with relatively high interest rates

4.2.1.2 Guidelines in Obtaining Farm Credit

1. Know your credit needs. Plan your project well. Consult your loan officer about the credit needs of your project.
2. Prepare your farm plan and budget. This can be done through the help of a production technician. To accomplish a good farm plan and budget, one should keep a complete and accurate record of the resources, income, and expenses. The record should show the performance of the project during the previous years. Also, it will determine if the credit was applied properly.
3. Acquire loan from an authorized bank. It is advisable to get credit from only one bank for simplicity in planning one's credit needs. The bank employs an agricultural technician to assist borrowers on modern concepts and better methods of production.
4. Be honest in providing credit information. Inform the loan officer about the true facts of the project and its financial requirements.
5. Use the credit for the intended project. The loan should be used only in accordance with the approved farm plan and budget. Borrow only the actual cost of the project.
6. Prepare a repayment plan in advance. Before applying for a loan, one has to prepare a repayment plan. Repayments should come from incomes generated by the project such as the sale of crops or livestock. Limit the credit within one's ability to repay the loan.
7. Maintain good savings and repayment habits. Prompt repayment of one's credit enhances one's credit rating. If one saves regularly in the bank, one reduces dependence on credit. This is more economical.

4.2.1.3 Fund Management

Aside from identifying and assessing the possible sources for the business, a farmer or agribusiness owner should also know how to use or manage the funds of the business well. Fund management also involves fund control or the ability to monitor the use of the limited.

4.3 BASIC RECORD KEEPING (IMPORTANCE & TYPES OF RECORDS)

Record keeping is the systematic compilation of certain types of information. Reliable and accurate records are used to make better decisions affecting the farm. It is important for farmer enterprise group members to know what actions have been taken by the FEG, or what or how much has been bought, sold or repaid, baseline of each farmer, what was the contribution of each

farmer in the group, profit of each farmer according to their respective contribution. If these actions are not recorded, misunderstandings may develop between members. An important building block in group development, therefore, is record-keeping. Like other processes in group formation, the development of record-keeping is a step-by-step process.

Regarding value chain enterprise, it is important to record all incomes and costs as soon as they are incurred. These are then summarized periodically, e.g. by week, month, quarterly or annually. By comparing annual income to annual costs, you can determine whether you have made a profit or a loss over the year. Prices received from buyers every time a sale is made. This will help identify periods during the year when higher prices can be obtained, or buyers who offer a better price.

With this information, farmers can adjust production so that they have more produce available when prices are higher. Yields obtained and total sales (by volume and price) for products in order to enable comparison with previous years and forecasting for future years.

4.3.1 Types of farm records

Farm Planning Schedule: This details the planned farm activities and the tentative dates for carrying them out. The schedule should be among the first records a farm manager produces. An example of a farm planning schedule for starting a rice, poultry or aquaculture enterprise.

Farm Input Record: Input record details the materials purchased and invested in the business. This should include the name of the input, the date of purchase, the price of the input, the amount of input(s) obtained, the total expenditure and where possible the expected useful life of the input. Example of an input record for starting a rice, poultry or aquaculture enterprise

Farm Labour Record: This type of record details the labour used for the various tasks on the farm. Information in the record includes the activities, the period when the activities took place, the duration of the activities, the amount of labour used and the cost of the labour. Example of a labour record for a rice, poultry or aquaculture enterprise.

Farm Production record: This record details the output from the business in a given period. It is advisable to record information in the production records at regular intervals, e.g. weekly, bi-weekly, monthly or quarterly. Example of a monthly production record for a rice, poultry or aquaculture enterprise.

MODULE V: MARKETING

5.1 OBJECTIVES

1. Define marketing within the context of farm management, agribusiness or entrepreneurship.
2. Develop marketing strategies along product, place, price, and promotion (marketing mix) in farm management, agribusiness or entrepreneurship.

5.1.1 Time: 3 hours

5.1.2 Activities

- Lectures
- Discussion
- Videos
- Presentation
- Case studies

5.1.3 Learning Exercises (Brainstorming, group discussion,

5.1.4 Energizers

5.1.5 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop

5.1.6 Evaluation

5.2 MARKETING

Discussion of marketing concepts in this training module shall revolve around the 4Ps of marketing within the context of agribusiness. Collectively referred to as the **marketing mix**, the 4Ps are the factors that help a business to sell its product or service.

The four elements – the *four Ps of marketing* – are normally set apart as getting the right **product** to the market, at the right **price**, ensuring that **promotion** in terms of advertising and marketing for the product or service is right, and ensuring that the product or service is distributed to the most convenient **Place** for the consumers to buy it.

5.2.1 Farm Marketing

Marketing of farm products involves activities which facilitate the movement of products from the farm to the ultimate users. It requires good transportation and communication system in order to ensure an efficient transfer of farm products to the consumers. Likewise, processing, warehousing and storage facilities should be adequate to expand the benefits of raw products and stabilize supply of farm goods.

5.2.2 Marketing Defined

- In the traditional view, marketing was confined to activities which involved the physical transfer of goods and services from the producers to the consumers.
- This concept of marketing however has been replaced by a wider perspective to meet the demands of modern and complex business society. Under the modern setting, exchange does not only involve goods and services but also money, time, attention, energy, devotion, and the like.
- For agricultural economies in the rural areas, which do not even have the most basic marketing facilities, what is needed is an efficient transportation system for the farm products and understanding market behaviour to take advantage of good prices and reaching out to customers.

5.2. Functions of Marketing in Agribusiness

5.2.1 Assembling

These are activities which involve the gathering and consolidating of small quantities of products into larger lots. They begin at the farm until the products reach the consumers. Advantages of assembling are the following:

- Reduces transportation cost
- Economizes the cost of grading
- Helps in product processing
- Facilitates in filling specific orders of customers

5.2.2 Storage

It refers to the keeping of products over a period of time in a warehouse, cold storage plant, or other storage facilities. Its advantages are the following:

- Maintains an adequate supply for processing
- Takes advantage of expected increase in prices
- Preserves the products, especially the perishables
- Improves the quality of certain products such as tobacco etc
- Regulates the flow of supply, thus minimizing price fluctuations

5.2.3 Standardizing and grading

The sorting of products based on kind, quality and size is called grading. The establishment of these grades is standardization. The advantages of grading are the following:

- The need for inspection of the product by buyers is reduced or eliminated.
- The sale of the product by description is made easier.
- Cost of transportation is reduced.
- Appearance of the product is improved and thereby commands a better price

5.2.4 Transportation.

It is the movement of goods from one place to another. The presence of road and transportation systems facilitates the efficient movement of farm products to the different regions of the country.

5.2.5 Processing.

It is the transformation of a raw product into a more usable form. Products require processing to extend their life span and increase their market value. The advantages of processing are:

- Improves the quality of the product
- Makes the product more usable
- Prevents the contamination of the product
- Prolongs the perishability of the product
- Increases the nutrients of the product
- Provides the manufacture of by-products for consumption
- Transforms some raw products into other products, such as milk into cheese

5.2.5 Packaging.

This is the process of placing goods in bags, containers or wrappers. The advantages are the following:

- For easier handling
- Protects from possible damage
- Reduces storage and transportation cost
- Prevents loss of weight and food value

5.2.6 Retailing.

This is the ultimate selling of products to the final consumers. The advantages are the following:

- Provides consumers with various goods
- Keeps goods which are for immediate delivery
- Makes buying convenient for the consumers

5.3 BASIC PACKAGING FUNCTIONS:

1. Containment and protection
2. Usage
3. Communication
4. Segmentation

5.3.1 Factors Considered in Packaging Decisions

1. Package design – color, shape and material influence consumer perception about the company and the product. In selecting a package size, shelf life, convenience, and competition must be considered.
2. Package costs – based on a total and per-unit cost (various packaging materials entail different costs: paperboard, plastic, metal, glass, Styrofoam, and cellophane, among others)

5.4 MARKETING MIX (4PS OF MARKETING)

5.4.1 Place

location of the business is essential to either reduce cost, increase the chances of customers stopping at the business to look at the products or at least make inquiries. If the business is retail-oriented, it should be near the market. If it is production-oriented, it may be better to be close to its raw material sources or near infrastructure facilities, transport and utilities centers.

Important factors:

- Proximity to essential raw materials
- Proximity to markets and distribution channels
- Availability of transport facilities
- Availability of efficient and cheap skilled labor
- Existence of related industries
- Infrastructure facilities
- Communication facilities
-

5.4.2 Price

There are three common ways of determining the selling price of the product/service

5.4.3 Product

- Product planning involves new and existing products
- A new product may be a modification, a minor innovation, or a major innovation
- After innovation, products are managed from growth to decline
- New products offer differential advantages
- Creativity/Idea generation is the key to searching for new products opportunities

5.4.3.1 Branding-

An important part of product planning is branding. A brand is a name, design, or symbol that identifies the products of a seller or group of sellers.

Four types of brand designation:

- a. Brand name – a word, letter (number), group of words, or letters (numbers) than can be spoken
- b. Brand mark – a symbol, design, or distinctive colouring or lettering
- c. Trademark – a brand name or brand mark that is given legal protection

5.4.3.2 Importance of Branding

- Product identification is eased
- Customers are assured that a good or service has a certain level of quality
- A company is able to advertise its products in the buyer's mind
- Product prestige is increased as social visibility becomes meaningful

5.4.3.3 Effective Brand Names

- Suggests something about the product's use, benefit or attributes
- Easy to spell and remember and pronounceable in only one way
- Can be applied to a whole line of product line
- Capable of legal protection from use by others
- Has a pleasant or at least neutral meaning in international markets

Note: After branding and packaging comes the labelling. A label is used to identify, grade, describe and promote a product.

5.4.3.4. Product Life Cycle –

Stages of Product Life in The Market.

Introduction Stage: A period of slow sales growth as the product is introduced in the market. Profits are non-existent in this stage because of the heavy expenses incurred with product introduction.

Growth Stage: A period of rapid market acceptance and substantial profit improvement.

Maturity Stage: A period of slowdown in sales growth because the product has achieved acceptance of most potential buyers. Profits stabilize or decline because of increased marketing outlays to defend the product position.

Decline Stage: The period when sales show a downward drift and profits erode.

5.4.3 Promotion

This is one of the most neglected aspects of marketing a product. Promotion is necessary to encourage and convince buyers to purchase the product and not the competitors. Promotion is generally divided into advertising, sales promotion, and personal selling.

5.5 BASIC STEPS IN PLANNING THE MARKETING PROCESS

1. Situation analysis: Before developing any sort of action plan, decision makers should acquire information on the problems and opportunities imposed by input suppliers, other producers and its consumers. The business environment should be explored, including such areas as: i) technologies used; ii) cost structures within the industry; iii) regulations and standards affecting the business; as well as, iv) strengths and weaknesses of the enterprise itself.

2. Setting objectives: Based on the situation analysis specific targets need to be established with respect to anticipated future performance of the enterprise.

3. Developing strategies and action plans: To achieve the stated objectives enterprises should formulate and develop short- and long-term strategies.

4. Set up coordination and control mechanisms: These must be designed and implemented to guarantee effective implementation of the strategies and action plans.

5.6 MARKET INTELLIGENCE

Market intelligence is the permanent collection, analysis, monitoring, evaluation, storage and distribution of information on markets. It is a continuous process, which focuses on what happens outside the enterprise and provides on-going information about the market.

Information needs to be wide-ranging and diverse. It may include:

- i. Price information concerning raw materials and inputs.
- ii. Development of new processes and related inputs
- iii. Investments
- iv. Launch of new products
- v. information on competitors
- vi. Policies affecting enterprise' competitiveness
- vii. Promotional events.

There are several information sources, which are used by market intelligence agents: Internal company information: sales records, production costs, technical efficiency ratios, customer records, etc.

1. Suppliers, intermediaries and customers. These are excellent sources of information which should not to be left untapped.
2. Secondary information such as the press reviews, radio, television, trade fairs, advertising, official gazettes, newsletters from professional associations and chambers of business and industry.
3. Information on competitors, on prices, product qualities and promotion strategies.
4. National licensing or patent offices and research and development institutions.

D. Learning Exercises (SLEs)

1. What went right? What went wrong?
2. What were your targets? Did you attain them or not?
3. How would you describe the production process that you set up in your factory?
4. What were the superior systems employed by the winner?
5. What were the defects in the production system and processes?
6. What are the factors to be considered in marketing your product or service?
7. What did you learn from this exercise?
8. How can you apply these lessons in your own businesses?

MODULE VI: ENTERPRISE AND FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

6.1 OBJECTIVES

1. Acquire the necessary knowledge and skills for analyzing profitability of agribusiness enterprise
2. Estimate costs and revenue in agribusiness enterprise
3. Identify risks in agribusiness enterprise

6.1.1 Time: 3 hours

6.1.2 Activities

- Lectures
- Discussion
- Videos
- Presentation
- Case studies

6.1.3 Learning Exercises (Brainstorming, group discussion,

6.1.4 Energizers

6.1.5 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop

6.1.6 Evaluation

6.2 FARM BUSINESS PROFITABILITY

- Profitability is the primary goal of all business ventures.
- Measuring current and past profitability and projecting future profitability is very important.
- Profitability is measured with income and expenses. Income is money generated from the activities of the business. For example, if vegetables and livestock are produced and sold, income is generated.
- Expenses are the cost of resources used up or consumed by the activities of the business.
- The understanding about the profitability of enterprise is important, this relates to the identification of product, planning, procurement, management, and marketing, selling and developing strong relationship with the market.
- Cost analysis will enable the farmers to analyze the difference between traditional and business farming practices; these are the major reasons for computing profitability.
- Whether you are recording profitability for the past period or projecting profitability for the coming period, measuring profitability is the most important measure of the success of the business.
- A business that is not profitable cannot survive. Conversely, a business that is highly profitable has the ability to reward its owners with a large return on their investment.

- Increasing profitability is one of the most important tasks of the business-oriented farmers.

6.2.1 Gross Margin Analysis

- Gross margin budgets are usually expressed on a per hectare basis to allow for comparisons of different crops.
- Gross income consists of not only the produce sold, but also the produce consumed, given away e.g. as gifts, bartered, and retained produce still in storage, and even by-products (e.g. poultry manure).
- The Gross Income from harvest is estimated from multiplying saleable harvest by area of crop planted and the unit price that the farmers are likely to obtain, (taking into the season, and the local market conditions).
- The unit prices for produce and inputs that are used in the budget estimates usually come from different sources including suppliers of agricultural inputs, prices observed in local produce markets, agencies that provide information, extension personnel, and private companies and contracting companies.
- Variable costs are production costs directly allocated to a particular enterprise and usually change according to seasons, and size and scale of production. Examples include seed, fertilizers, agro-chemicals, casual or hired labour, packaging materials, land preparation and transport of inputs and produce.

6.2.2 Gross Income

Gross income can be increased by increasing the expected yield, the marketable yield, or the selling price.

1. The expected yield can be increased by selection of appropriate and high yielding varieties of the crop, as well as proper selection and use of other inputs such as fertilizers and chemicals.
2. Weeding, irrigating and pest and disease control, can result in increased yields which in turn can lead to increased income.
3. Increased yields can also be achieved by reducing field losses.
4. The marketable yield can be increased by correct harvesting and timing of harvest, correct post-harvest handling and transportation of produce, all contribute towards reducing post-harvest losses.
5. An increase in the pack-out percentage, for example, would increase the marketed yield. Pack out percentage refers to the proportion of the marketable produce after considering yield losses.
6. The selling price can be improved by synchronizing production to coincide with periods when the market price is high, or, for products that you can store such as rice, to sell when the price is high. High prices are also usually obtainable when the quality of the produce is high, e.g. it may be better to grade product according to market requirements, and get premium prices for the high grades, rather than having a mixture of grades thereby getting an average price.

6.2.3 Total Variable Costs

In assessing the viability of the enterprise, the farmer can increase the gross margin by carefully analysing total variable costs and eliminating those that are not necessary. For example, if the farmer is not applying the recommended quantity of inputs due to inadequate knowledge, he/she could seek extension advice to address that gap. By applying the correct quantity of inputs, and not over applying, the farmer could reduce the total variable costs.

Careful planning and management of labour can also help in reducing total variable costs.

6.2.4 Break-Even analysis

Break-even analysis determines the level at which total revenue equals total cost. A farmer may also want to know the minimum price per kg that should be charged in order to cover production costs (break–even price) and the minimum yield/quantity she could expect per ha of potato in order to cover the costs (break–even yield/quantity).

6.3 ASSESSING AND MANAGING RISK IN AGRIBUSINESS

Although Business farming is significantly profitable business, but every business has risk factors. However, just which risks pose the greatest challenge is highly dependent upon what enterprises you engage in and what stage your business is in. It is important to identify and assess the potential risks at all level. Risks also depends upon the nature of value chain and location. The following are the potential risk areas to be considered during decision making process.

1. Production
2. Market and Marketing
3. Financial risk
4. Human Resources

Risk is defined as any factor that may cause losses to the farm business. Farmers may control these through better management and optimal usage of their resources. Some risks are external, such as changes in market prices, low rainfall, etc. Some risks are internal, such as decisions about what to produce, the type of inputs to purchase and use, etc. While farmers can control the internal risks more easily, there are ways to also manage external risks, provided these are recognized and addressed in time. However, risk management is not a guarantee for success, and often allows the farmer to effectively minimize the negative effects to his/her business.

6.3.1 Risk Management Strategies

- Use of risk reduction input
- Use of risk reduction technology
- Selection of low risk activities
- Allow for system flexibility
- Production diversification
- Reserve of input and product
- Spreading sales
- Market price information
- Engaging in contract farming
- Selling assets

MODULE VI: COOPERATIVES

6.1 OBJECTIVES

1. Understand the concept of cooperatives
2. Acquire basic skill of cooperative formation
- 3.

6.1.1 Time: 3 hours

6.1.2 Activities

- Lectures
- Discussion
- Videos
- Presentation
- Case studies

6.1.3 Learning Exercises (Brainstorming, group discussion,

6.1.4 Energizers

6.1.5 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop

6.1.6 Evaluation

6.2 INTRODUCTION TO COOPERATIVES

In today's world, the power of groups in agricultural and rural development cannot be overemphasized. Presently the use of groups in agricultural development is increasing all over the world. It has now become a policy of many governmental and non-governmental organizations, operating in rural and in urban areas, to request people to organize themselves into viable groups, before they can be eligible to participate or benefit from the activities of such organizations. Why do these organizations insist that the people must form groups? Why do they prefer working with groups instead of working with individuals? Indeed, there are very good reasons for this development, as we will read in the next section of this manual.

6.2.1 Meaning and Importance of Social Groups and Cooperatives

A group is simply a collection of people who came together to provide unity of action for the achievement of a common objective.

There are two types of groups:

1. formal groups
2. informal groups.

Formal groups are purposely created in order to pursue a specific task, while informal groups usually form naturally in response to the situation or interests of their members. A typical example of an informal group is the family. While we can learn a lot from informal groups in terms of leadership and motivation, in this manual, we will concentrate mostly on formal groups, whose leaders usually operate by member appointment and delegated authority and responsibility.

A cooperative group is a formal voluntary self-selected group of people who operate as a business on a non-profit or cost basis. Cooperatives serve as a legal, practical means by which a group of individuals seek to promote and improve their economic interests in a competitive society. Therefore, cooperatives can be viewed as a way of doing business – but it is business with a difference, because their formation and operation must be in accordance with laid down cooperative laws and principles of a country. The importance of cooperatives are:

- a. **Reduction of costs.** Collective bargaining power enables the members to get lower cost of services, thereby saving money and increasing their efficiency.
- b. **Owner control.** The members own and control the cooperative.
- c. **Service at minimal cost.** Cooperatives operate on the basis of maximum service to members at minimal cost
- d. **Greater access to inputs and services.** Through collective power, members may use the cooperative to obtain better supplies of inputs such as fertilizer, to get better market prices, etc.
- e. **Empowerment of the poor in the society.** They are platforms through which the weak and the poor in the society can come together, harness their resources and be able to participate in economic development process.
- f. **Economies of scale.** They have some of the benefits of companies and more. Higher productivity can be stimulated through cooperatives.
- g. **Building of democratic institutions.** Although small, local cooperative groups provide ideal environment for the diffusion of collective decision-making and leadership skills, which can be used in subsequent development of larger associations/federations.
- h. **Political participation.** Politically, participation in group activity provides opportunities for farmers to contribute constructively to development.
- i. **Sustainability.** Participation in groups leads to self-reliance among small farmers and the establishment of self-sustaining rural organizations.

6.3 FORMATION OF COOPERATIVES

Farmer groups, farmer cooperatives and farmer social groups can be organized in generally the same way. However, depending on location and the specific social setting the general steps to take in organizing a small farmer group or cooperatives can be outlined as shown in the table below.

The group	TASKS TO BE ACCOMPLISHED BY THE ORGANIZER
1. Felt Needs	Peoples ideas and motives Economic situation, e.g. income, better services, etc
2. Appoint an organizing Committee	Social mobilization Sensitization, awareness creation Conduct of meetings, lectures, talks Contact with resource persons/organization
3. Conduct Economic and Social Survey	Carry out a feasibility survey Use a sound decision criterion to Compare felt needs, availability, culture, norms, potential business, profitability Prepare a feed back to the group or community
4. Convene a Feedback Meeting	Publicize meeting well in advance Present survey results and recommendations Discuss every finding Get people's views and commitment
5. Group Bye Laws	Prepare group bye laws Obtain help from an expert or the Coop Dept
6. Registration	Obtain and fill all registration forms correctly Submit all the requirements for registration e.g. minutes book, records
7. Conduct Election of Board Members	Successful reg. ends the tenure of the Organizing Committee It dissolves itself & call for election of group's BOARD members BOARD elects its chairman

Once the group or cooperative is formed it should settle down to face its business. It should pre-occupy itself with the questions of how to achieve its aims and objectives. The members should come together to figure out how to increase their access to needed resources and services. E.g. more farm inputs at affordable prices, more credit at affordable price and better access to markets and commodity prices.

6.4 COOPERATIVE MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONS

1. Planning
2. Organizing
3. Directing
4. Coordinating
5. Controlling.

The goal of a cooperative management is to apply the resources at its disposal to get things done through other people in order to realize its goals efficiently. To achieve this end the manager utilizes the cooperative 's resources at his command, namely labour (people), capital, etc through these processes or functions in order to attain the cooperative's goals.

That is to say, for the cooperative management to take the group to its destinations (e.g. increased access to credit, input sourcing, market access, etc), it has to:

Plan the group 's various needs and wants ahead

Organize the group 's resources in a workable and realistic mode,

Direct others, delegate or lead in the process of getting needs or things being one,

Coordinate and Control, integrate the process and the resources, so they function as a unified whole, and **Control**, appraise and evaluate performance so as to remedy constraints and ensure steady progress or action.

To perform these five functions effectively the group leaders require technical as well as executive skills. They must possess knowledge of their job, administrative skills, experience to go with the job, understanding of cooperatives principles and capacity to work with others including knowledge of managing inter-group activities and synergy.

A key requirement for success of a group is management. Poor management has resulted in failure and disintegration of several groups. Success in management therefore depends on group's ability to plan, organize, direct, coordinate and control its activities effectively, in order to enable it to achieve its goals. In the changing macro-economic and political situation of Nigeria, farmer groups and cooperatives can play vital roles in influencing and shaping the course of national socio-economic development. By organizing, they have greater potential to explore new markets, diversify their strategies and products, achieve increased political participation, and exert greater influence on public decisions that affect their interests.

MODULE VI: LEADERSHIP

7.1 OBJECTIVES

1. To have an overview of leadership skills that is basic to manage cooperatives, farm businesses and agribusiness.
2. To explore definitions of leadership and characteristics of good leaders
3. To broaden perspective about who is and who can be a leader.

7.1.1 Time: 3 hours

7.1.2 Activities

- Lectures
- Discussion
- Videos
- Presentation
- Case studies

7.1.3 Learning Exercises (Brainstorming, group discussion,

7.1.4 Energizers

7.1.5 Materials

- Flip charts
- Markers
- Masking tape
- Projector
- Laptop

7.1.6 Evaluation

7.2 LEADERSHIP AND AGRIBUSINESS MANAGEMENT

7.2.1 Leadership vs. Management

Clearly, leadership does not only entail the usual managerial role of organizing, directing and combining resources to produce a desired quantity and quality of output. Leadership involves engaging, and ultimately inspiring people to have a sense of ownership of the team's goals. A leader innovates and strategizes, even if at times, it goes beyond the usual routine and established rules. Farming especially in rural areas requires guidance and inspiration from community and cooperative leaders to grow and regenerate into a viable venture.

7.2.2 Who is a leader? (Azarbaijani – Moghaddam, 2007)

A good leader makes a good team/group/organization. A good leader should have adequate information about the dynamics of the team/group/organization and the entire value chain to which the team/group/organization is integrated (whether closely or loosely). A good leader should possess a strong personality to command obedience and respect from people. A good leader exudes respectable character, with strong

managerial skills. A good leader has an honest disposition towards self, work and others.

A good leader must have inclusive, participatory and horizontal leadership. This type of leadership rests on the ability to engage in certain leadership strategies, most importantly: communication, listening, building consensus, creating shared meaning, and developing learning partnerships.

- **Communication:** leadership begins with communication. Leaders should be skilled in conveying their ideas and skills to others. Good leaders are good at observing, articulating and communicating.
- **Listening:** Leaders are strengthened by listening to the perspective and objectives of others. Listening is not confined to hearing what a supervisor, colleague or competitor says but includes valuing and giving credit to their suggestions and opinions. An effective listener, like an effective leader, is one who learns from what she/he hears.
- **Building Consensus:** Building consensus is an important decision-making process for successful leadership. Through dialogue, members of a team/group/organization come to understand the points upon which they agree. Decisions are formulated with a mutual understanding of options and possibilities. Where differences of opinion remain, no action is taken by the team/group/organization. Although at times, consensus building can be frustrating and time-consuming, it leads to agreed-upon decisions that everyone can support and follow.
- **Creating Shared Meaning:** Small groups and large institutions can benefit from the creation of shared meaning. Through dialogue, consensus building, and shared experience, a core set of values and principles evolves in which everyone has to some degree participated in formulating and in which everyone has a stake. Shared meaning is an adaptive and flexible approach to goal setting that is influenced by a group's composition and the passage of time. When a group creates shared meaning, each member operates within a framework in which she shares ownership and responsibility. This is a requirement for cooperative or group of farmers that aspire to be competitive, productive and continue to grow along a given value chain.
- **Developing Learning Partnerships:** The outcome of a partnership reflects the thinking and activities of its participants. Developing learning partnerships is an inward looking, collective-learning approach to institutional development. It involves self-awareness and self-reflection as well as group awareness and group reflection for the individuals carrying out the partnership's purpose and activities. Hence, a learning partnership is one in which the participants' interactions result in reflection, evaluation, self-criticism, and knowledge that enhances or accelerates reaching the partnership's objectives. Learning partnerships create dynamic, participatory, and highly productive working environments in which everyone gains knowledge while learning to increase their own and the partnership's capabilities.

8.0 APPENDIXE

Drafting of First Strategic Business Plan

With the model and strategy (strategic direction) decided, it is time to draft through the narrative of the plan's many sections.

BUSINESS PLAN FORMAT

1. BUSINESS DESCRIPTION

- 1.1. The Nature of the Business and Business Trends
 - 1.1.1. The Nature of the Business (The Business idea / Model)
 - 1.1.2. The Industry Structure & trends (Industry Analysis)
- 1.2. The Enterprise (Farmer Organization)
 - 1.2.1. The name of the cooperative
 - 1.2.2. The Business Mission and Vision
 - 1.2.3. The Business Goals (and Objectives)
 - 1.2.4. Type of Business ownership & share capital
 - 1.2.5. Business location
- 1.3. The product and Services
- 1.4. Opportunity & Entry Strategies

2. MARKET ANALYSIS, INDUSTRY ANALYSIS, & MARKET PLANS

- 2.1. Industry & Market Research and Analysis
 - 2.1.1. Major Customers
 - 2.1.2. Market size
 - 2.1.3. Market and Industry trends
 - 2.1.4. Major Competitors
 - 2.1.5. Entry Barriers
- 2.2. Marketing Plan
 - 2.2.1. Overall marketing strategy (From the 4 Ps)
 - 2.2.2. Pricing Strategy and Policies
 - 2.2.3. Sales tactics
 - 2.2.4. Advertising and promotion
 - 2.2.5. Distribution plan

3. ORGANISATIONAL, MANAGEMENT & OPERATIONAL PLANS

- 3.1. Design and Development Plans
 - 3.1.1. Development Status and Tasks
 - 3.1.2. Design and development costs
 - 3.1.3. Major difficulty and risks
- 3.2. Production and Operation Plans (Done in a later activity)
 - 3.2.1. (Production plans & calendars) & Harvest schedules.
 - 3.2.2. Operations & Aggregation planning
 - 3.2.3. Facilities and capacities
- 3.3. Organizational and management team
 - 3.3.1. Organizational structure (now & the ideal)

- 3.3.2. Key management personnel
- 3.3.3. Supporting Advisors and services

4. FINANCIAL ANALYSIS AND PLAN (Done in a later activity)

- 4.1. The Economics of Business
 - 4.1.1. Major Fixed and Variable Costs
 - 4.1.2. Break even calculations and Analysis
 - 4.1.3. Gross and Operating margins Analysis
- 4.2. Financial Projections and Plans
 - 4.2.1. Projected Income Statement
 - 4.2.2. Projected Cash Flow Statement
 - 4.2.3. Projected balance Sheet
- 4.3. Proposed Enterprise Financing
 - 4.3.1. Desired Financing (Needs)
 - 4.3.2. Capitalization (Sources)
 - 4.3.3. Use of Funds (Uses)